

Teaching Primary Classes On The Basis Of An Integrated Approach

Abdurakhmanova Shahzodakhan

4th grade student of Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi

abdurakhmonova.shahzodaxon@gmail.com

Abstract: *This article is about teaching elementary school students based on an integrated approach.*

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INTRODUCTION.

Currently, all spheres of the life of New Uzbekistan have entered the field of deep reforms. It is no secret to any of us that in this process, changes in the education system, which is considered one of the foundations of the social sphere, are also clearly visible. In recent years, practical work on organizing all stages of the education system based on modern requirements has entered a decisive stage in our country.

As President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "The more educated our children are, the faster economic sectors based on high technologies will develop, the more social problems will be solved." Therefore, if I say that the threshold of New Uzbekistan starts from the school, I think that our entire nation will support this idea."

In particular, the development of innovation and integration in science is of high value. In comprehensive schools, integration means the inclusion and support of students with different backgrounds, abilities and needs in the same educational environment. This concept aims to create an inclusive and diverse learning environment where every student is valued and supported regardless of their differences. Comprehensive schools play a critical role in fostering inclusion by offering a wide range of classes and methods designed to meet the needs of all students. This often involves creating a supportive and inclusive school culture, providing special education and support for students with disabilities or learning differences, and developing a cohesive and diverse community. takes

The concept of integration is defined as the aspect of the development process and the integration of elements. Integration is characterized by an increase in the volume and intensity of relations and interactions between elements, their regulation and the emergence of qualitatively new features, turning into a certain integrated education.

Svetlovskaya N. N. believes that integration is the process of adapting some elements or parts of various types of educational activities into a whole, provided that they are functionally identical.

Primary schools can work with families and the wider community to promote inclusion by involving parents, carers

and community members in school activities and decision-making processes. Such an inclusive approach allows for greater community involvement and support, leading to a more cohesive and integrated school environment.

Integration in primary classrooms also aims to improve the professional competence of teachers and staff, providing them with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively support students from different backgrounds and needs. This may include training in integrated teaching practices and strategies to support students with learning disabilities.

In general, integration in the Primary classrooms is an ongoing and multifaceted process that requires a commitment to diversity, equity and inclusion from all members of the school community. By creating an integrated learning environment, providing tailored support for students with diverse needs, and encouraging partnerships with families and the community, comprehensive schools promote inclusion and foster inclusive and supportive learning for all students. -can play an important role in creating a supportive learning environment.

At present, there are different views on the issue of studying integrated pedagogy, among which the most effective way is explained as a system that allows students to break the knowledge of the "nature + human" system based on integrated sciences. Because at the beginning of the 21st century, there is such a situation in the life of the society that now every person living on earth needs to master the spiritual and ecological concepts. Until now, it has become clear that the unplanned use of natural resources can make mistakes in human life in the future. Therefore, it is considered that the main task of integrated courses should be the education of ecological spirituality. Such an idea aims to explain to young people the unity on earth, the struggle for a single goal, the unity of man and nature, and the connection between the life of man and nature with the laws of the galactic system.

It is necessary to implement integrated education based on internal logical connection and deeper methodological connections. Also, in the content of integrated sciences, which is emerging now, there is a possibility of merging ideas related to different philosophical currents into a single point. Because now not only the natural adaptation of the bordering sciences, but also the small continental (one group of sciences with other

group of sciences) adaptation is being mastered in the philosophy of education.

Integrating education in school is an approach that combines the study of different subjects and disciplines in one lesson or educational process. This approach allows you to encourage a deeper understanding of the material, develop critical thinking, and integrate knowledge from different fields.

Russian pedagogical scientists T. Kun, V.S. Styopin's research tried to integrate the sciences of philosophy, nature and culture. They propose to apply the sciences of physics and cybernetics to explain phenomena in the inorganic world and to solve problems in biology and chemistry.

Also, in the current pedagogical practice, research on the integration of education on the basis of interdisciplinarity continues. This task is extremely complex and at the same time can be very fruitful.

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the tasks of education in all-round development of young people in our society are broad and multifaceted. A pedagogue should approach his profession with responsibility not only in terms of education, but also in terms of upbringing.

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